

BRAND LOYALTY TOWARD LOCAL FOOTWEAR BRANDS: THE ROLE OF SELF-IMAGE CONGRUENCE, ETHNOCENTRISM, AND INFLUENCER MARKETING AMONG GEN Z

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Abstract. Indonesia's local footwear industry is currently facing a critical threat due to the surge of illegal imports, which undermines the competitiveness of domestic brands. This issue poses a serious challenge to brand loyalty, especially in the middle to lower consumer segments, where price sensitivity often outweighs long-term emotional attachment to brands. This study investigates the influence of self-image congruence, consumer ethnocentrism, and influencer marketing on customer satisfaction and brand loyalty toward local footwear brands among Generation Z in Jabodetabek. Using a quantitative method and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), data were collected from 205 Gen Z respondents who had purchased local footwear brands. The analysis revealed that none of the proposed hypotheses were statistically supported, either directly or indirectly. These findings suggest a shift in Gen Z consumer behavior in Indonesia, emphasizing pragmatic values such as price sensitivity and trend adaptation over identity-driven or nationalistic motives. The study highlights the need for localized marketing strategies that reflect the economic realities and preferences of Gen Z in emerging markets.

Keywords: Self Image Congruence, Consumer Ethnocentrism, Influencer Marketing, Fashion, Generation Z, Footwear

1 Introduction

The footwear industry has grown significantly, driven by consumer awareness of local products and evolving fashion trends. Generation Z, a key market segment, views sneakers as a means of self-expression, making them one of the most distinct footwear categories. Generation Z uses sneakers to show their personality when choosing unique designs and brands. Sneakers are also one of the product categories that have special characteristics compared to other objects in the world of footwear, such as formal shoes or other casual shoes (Pradana, et, al., 2024). According to World Population Review (2024), over 22 billion pairs of shoes are produced annually, with China leading global production, followed by Vietnam and Indonesia. Despite Indonesia's strong production capacity, the rise of illegal imports threatens local brands, particularly in the middle and lower market segments. This situation is also reinforced by data discrepancies between Indonesia's Central Statistics Agency or Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS) and the International Trade Center (ITC), there is a significant issue with illegal shoe imports from China. Significant discrepancies in import data—such as a US\$441 million gap between BPS and ITC in 2023—highlight the scale of illegal imports from China. In 2022, this gap was even larger, with Indonesia's footwear imports at US\$883.22 million based on BPS data and over US\$883.22 million according to ITC data, marking that year as having the

highest level of illegal imports. These imports, including counterfeit and under-invoiced goods, are sold at lower prices, shifting consumer behavior and making it harder for local brands to compete (Pramita, 2024; CNBC Indonesia, 2024). The impact of illegal imports is evident, as Indonesia lost two major footwear manufacturers, PT Dean Shoes and PT Sepatu Bata Tbk (BATA), between April 2023 and April 2024 due to declining demand and economic challenges. PUBEX (2024) reported a 19.77% drop in local footwear sales, highlighting the challenges faced by domestic brands. Statista (2024) estimates Indonesia's footwear industry revenue at USD 5.19 billion in 2024, expected to grow to USD 5.79 billion by 2025. However, economic slowdowns in key export markets may lower demand for Indonesian footwear (Permata Bank, 2024). The research discusses how Indonesia's local footwear industry faces intense competition from illegal imports, making it crucial for brands to implement strategies that enhance customer satisfaction and build brand loyalty. On previous studies, self-image congruence (Heo et al., 2023; Suyoto & Tannady, 2022), consumer ethnocentrism (Sharma et al., 1995), and influencer marketing (Salim, 2024; Hudders & Lou, 2022) are considered key drivers in building brand loyalty, directly and indirectly through customer satisfaction to reduce brand switching and strengthening long-term loyalty (Uddin et al., 2017; Silva et al., 2020). This study aims to examine the impact of these factors on customer satisfaction and brand loyalty in the local footwear industry. Due to the limited research on these factors within the context of local footwear brands, this study aims to help the industry stay competitive, particularly among Generation Z in Indonesia.

2 Literature Review

2.1. Brand Loyalty

According to Afroz et al (2023), **brand loyalty** is not just about repeat purchases, but also involves a deeper bond where the customer aligns their personal values or identity with the brand's image. The more loyal customers there are the stronger position the brand has in the market and there are less vulnerable clients who would be willing to switch brands they regularly purchase products from (Silva et al., 2020). Customers will continue to make purchases without being affected by the increase in prices due to customers thinking that other brands do not have better quality (Clarisa et al., 2023). In the context of the Indonesian Generation Z consumer, various factors influence brand loyalty, including self-image congruence (Parwati et al., 2021), consumer ethnocentrism (Elrayah & Piaralal, 2024), and influencer marketing (Sakshitha et al., 2024). These factors create emotional connections and shape consumer preferences toward local footwear brands.

2.2. Self-Image Congruence and Brand Loyalty

Self-image congruence refers to the alignment between a consumer's self perception and the image of a brand, which influences brand loyalty (Heo et al., 2023). This alignment is reflected in three dimensions: Actual self-congruence, where the brand reflects the consumer's current self-image (Vigolo, 2016, as cited in AlQahtani, 2025); Ideal self-congruence, where the brand helps the consumer achieve their aspirational self (Yuanita & Marsasi, 2022); and Social self-congruence, where the brand aligns with the consumer's desired social identity (Wiweko & Ferdinand, 2025). This connection is crucial for Gen Z, as they often use fashion and footwear to express their personalities and align with desired social identities. Baskara & Marsasi (2023) defined these congruences as the

correlation between a consumer's personality & feelings about a product or service that drive brand loyalty. Authenticity and transparency enhance self-congruity by aligning brand values with consumers' self-concept, fostering trust and strengthening brand loyalty (AlQahtani, 2025). Based on these findings, the researcher proposes the following hypothesis.

H1: Self-image congruence will positively influence brand loyalty.

2. 3. Consumer Ethnocentrism and Brand Loyalty

Consumer ethnocentrism is related to the field of consumer behavior and international marketing (Chaudhry et al, 2020), and is closely tied to two key dimensions: national pride and economic patriotism. For ethnocentric consumers, buying imported products is seen as morally wrong, as it is believed to harm the local economy, reduce jobs, and be unpatriotic (Bartikowski et al, 2020). National pride is reflected in the consumer's belief that buying domestic products supports the national economy, fostering a sense of pride in contributing to local growth and feeling proud when buying local brands over imported ones (Abosag & Farah, 2014, as cited in Chaudhry et al, 2020). According to Sipahi et al (2023), ethnocentric tendencies involve viewing one's own culture as superior, being wary of other cultures, seeking group respect, and emphasizing cultural distinctiveness. Economic patriotism highlights a moral preference for domestic products to support the local economy, even if the quality is not always superior to imported goods (Wang & Chen's, 2004, as cited in Sipahi et al 2023). Consumers with high ethnocentric tendencies prefer domestically produced products, sometimes even experiencing guilt when forced to opt for foreign-made alternatives (Baber et al, 2024). According to previous research, the second hypothesis is as follows.

H2: Consumer ethnocentrism will positively influence brand loyalty.

2. 4. Influencer Marketing and Brand Loyalty

Influencer marketing is a strategy where brands collaborate with individuals who have a strong online presence to promote their products or services (Salim, 2024). According to Hudders & Lou (2022), influencer marketing is a digital advertising strategy that relies on social media users with large and engaged audiences to promote brands and products. Influencer-sponsored content is often seen by consumers as authentic recommendations, enhancing credibility and shaping positive brand perceptions. By leveraging their trust and authenticity, influencers strengthen emotional connections with followers, fostering brand loyalty through increased engagement and repeat purchases (Gökerik, 2024). This strategy ultimately enhances brand reputation and customer retention. By leveraging the trust influencers have built with their followers, reputable brands can establish consumer trust and loyalty (Valmohammadi et al, 2024). Therefore, the third hypothesis is as follows.

H3: Influencer marketing will positively influence brand loyalty.

2. 5. Customer Satisfaction as a Mediator

Customer satisfaction is often seen as a key mediator between various factors such as self-image congruence, consumer ethnocentrism, influencer marketing, and brand loyalty. According to Shiddiqi and Saiffudin (2023), **customer satisfaction** must be considered in order to gain the loyalty of customers. This concept is closely related to two dimensions of satisfaction: emotional satisfaction and value satisfaction. Emotional satisfaction is achieved when the product not only meets functional expectations but also provides positive consumer emotional experiences,

such as feeling good while using the product, enjoying the product, and being emotionally pleased with the brand (Uddin et al., 2017). On the other hand, value satisfaction focuses on the perceived fairness between the price paid and the benefits received, where consumers believe the product is worth the price, gives good value, and satisfies their expectations for quality relative to cost (Supriatna et al., 2022). Customer satisfaction reflects how well a product or service meets or exceeds customer expectations. Prioritizing satisfaction not only boosts brand loyalty but also helps prevent customers from switching to competitors. Based on these findings, the researcher proposes four additional hypotheses as follows.

H4: Customer satisfaction will positively influence brand loyalty.

H5: Self-image congruence will positively influence brand loyalty through customer satisfaction.

H6: Customer ethnocentrism will positively influence brand loyalty through customer satisfaction.

H7: Influencer marketing will positively influence brand loyalty through customer satisfaction.

Figure 1. Hypothesised Research Model

3 Research Method

This study applied a quantitative approach, which emphasized numerical data collection and statistical analysis, as the analytical tool. The primary objective is to test hypotheses regarding the influence of SIC, CE, and IM, on CS and BL. The sample was selected by considering the characteristics of Generation Z respondents in Jabodetabek (Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi) who have experienced purchasing local footwear products. Generation Z is defined as individuals born between 1997 and 2012. Researcher collected the data needed through Google form. A total of 213 respondents participated in the study, whose ages ranged from 13 and 28 years. However only 205 respondents met the criteria, while 8 other respondents were crossed out. On a Likert scale with five points, this questionnaire is ranging from 1 “strongly disagree” to 5 “strongly agree”. Respondents were asked to indicate where they agreed or disagreed with the statements made in the survey.

This study utilized a quantitative data processing application called SmartPLS 4, and Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) is used in the application for equation methods. The significance of relationships within the structural model was evaluated using PLS-SEM, with further examination through bootstrapping procedure encompassing 5000 samples. The profile of the respondents is shown in Table 1 with the classification of gender, age, and domicile. Within the sample, a significant majority were female, with 134 respondents or 65.37%. Meanwhile, male respondents are 77, with 34.63% of the overall sample. The significant dominance of female

participants in this research sample, aligns with market trends showing that women are more involved in purchasing local footwear products (Nursilowati & Mayangsari, 2020).

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	71	34.63%
	Female	134	65.37%
Age (years)	13-16	4	1.95%
	17-21	150	73.17%
	22-28	51	24.88%
	>28	0	0.00%
Domicile	Jakarta	51	24.88%
	Tangerang	53	25.85%
	Bogor	30	14.63%
	Depok	31	15.12%
	Bekasi	38	18.54%

4 Data Analysis and Discussions

4.1. Reliability and Validity Analysis

The measurement model (outer model) was evaluated, and the results are shown in Table 2. Table of reliability and validity analysis presents Cronbach's alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) to ensure the indicators reliably measure all constructs. The results show that the Cronbach's alpha for all constructs exceeds the recommended threshold of 0.7, indicating that the indicators used to measure these variables are highly reliable. The AVE values, which used to measure the validity, are well above the minimum threshold of 0.5, suggesting that the indicators adequately explain the constructs.

Table 2. Reliability and Validity Analysis

Construct	α	CR (rho_a)	CR (rho_c)	AVE
SIC	0.910	0.986	0.930	0.728
CE	0.893	0.904	0.920	0.698
IM	0.940	0.961	0.949	0.699
CS	0.924	0.939	0.940	0.724
BL	0.862	0.886	0.906	0.707

Note: α = Cronbach's alpha; CR = Composite Reliability; AVE = Average Variance Extracted.

Table 3 shows the results of discriminant validity. It was assessed using the HTMT (Heterotrait-monotrait) ratio, ensuring that each construct was uncorrelated or different from the others (Badgaiyan et al, 2016, as cited in Putri et al, 2022). The discriminant validity analysis in Table 3 shows low correlations between the constructs BL, CE, CS,

IM, and SIC, indicating they are distinct from one another. This distinctiveness is essential to accurately interpret the relationships in the study, avoiding confusion caused by overlapping constructs.

Table 3. Discriminant Validity Analysis

	BL	CE	CS	IM	SIC
BL					
CE	0.111				
CS	0.126	0.121			
IM	0.123	0.063	0.118		
SIC	0.054	0.080	0.092	0.065	

4. 2. Hypothesis Testing

The structural model (inner model) results, as shown in Table 4, reveal that none of the proposed direct or indirect relationships among variables reached statistical significance. For instance, H1 (SIC → BL) yielded a p-value of 0.648, exceeding the 0.05 threshold, indicating no significant effect. Similarly, H2 (CE → BL), H3 (IM → BL), and H4 (CS → BL) were also rejected. Indirect paths in H5, H6, and H7 failed to demonstrate significance as well, with all t-values below 1.96 and p-values above 0.05, indicating that CS does not mediate the effects of SIC, CE, or IM on BL in this research.

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Path	β	M	STDEV	t-values	p-values	Result
H1	SIC → BL	-0.040	-0.043	0.087	0.456	0.648	Rejected
H2	CE → BL	0.102	0.107	0.092	1.109	0.267	Rejected
H3	IM → BL	-0.106	-0.116	0.076	1.407	0.160	Rejected
H4	CS → BL	-0.108	-0.112	0.075	1.445	0.149	Rejected
H5	SIC → CS → BL	-0.010	-0.011	0.014	0.726	0.468	Rejected
H6	CE → CS → BL	-0.013	-0.014	0.013	0.946	0.344	Rejected
H7	IM → CS → BL	-0.015	-0.016	0.015	0.993	0.321	Rejected

Note: β = Standard Beta; M = Sample mean, STDEV = Standard Deviation

As shown in Table 4, BL was not significantly affected by SIC, CE, or IM, either direct or indirectly. For instance, SIC showed no significant path to BL (β=-0.040, p>0.05), and its mediating effect through CS was similarly weak. These unexpected findings indicate the emergence of a new phenomenon in the consumer behavior of Generation Z in Indonesia, diverging from theoretical assumptions that have previously shown consistent significance in other

global contexts. Unlike in developed countries, where studies often show strong correlations between SIC, CE, and IM (Heo et al., 2023; Chaudhry et al., 2020; Hudders et al., 2022), Indonesian Gen Z may prioritize pragmatic factors over identity-driven or nationalistic motives. In contrast, Indonesian Gen Z consumers, particularly those in middle-to-lower economic segments, appear more driven by pragmatic considerations such as price sensitivity, trend alignment, and functional benefits. This is supported by recent findings from Azizi & Raharjo (2024) and CRIF Indonesia (2024), which indicate that price sensitivity, trend adaptation, and economic pressure shape the purchasing behavior of Indonesian youth, particularly in the local footwear context, where decisions are driven more by affordability and functionality than by emotional or nationalistic brand attachments. Therefore SIC, which has been positively linked to BL in studies from more economically advanced settings (Heo et al., 2023; Suyoto & Tannady, 2022), cannot be applied for Indonesian Gen Z, whose BL is more price-sensitive.

The same pattern applies to CE, which traditionally reflects national pride and moral preference for local products (Chaudhry et al., 2020), showed no significant effect on BL in this context ($\beta=0.102$, $p>0.05$). Many studies emphasize the significant role of CE in shaping BL, particularly in more developed or Western markets (Sipahi et al., 2023; Bartikowski et al., 2020). However, this is consistent with the findings of Wang & Chen (2004), where CE had a lower impact in developing economies like Indonesia, as compared to high-income countries, and is further supported by Syah et al. (2022), who found that Indonesian Gen Z consumers are more likely to engage with footwear brands based on trends and higher in perceived value rather than emotional or identity-based motivations, contrary to the ethnocentric preference for local products seen in more developed markets. Although previous studies such as Sakshitha (2024) suggest that IM is an effective strategy for building BL across different demographic groups, this study found no significant direct ($\beta=-0.106$, $p>0.05$) or indirect ($\beta=-0.105$, $p>0.05$) effect of IM on BL. This discrepancy may be attributed to growing consumer skepticism among Gen Z, where influencer fatigue and perceived inauthenticity have diminished the persuasive impact of endorsements. These findings are consistent with Valmohammadi et al. (2024), who emphasize that authenticity and emotional engagement are essential in IM, but these elements are often perceived as lacking in the saturated Indonesia's influencer ecosystem. CS, a mediator that reflects consumers' emotional connection and perceived long-term value, failed to mediate the relationship between variables ($\beta=-0.108$, $p>0.05$) due to the pragmatic motivations driving Gen Z consumers in Indonesia. However, in Indonesia's market, especially among Gen Z, CS is often outweighed by price sensitivity, trend adaptation, and impulsive buying (Azizi & Raharjo, 2024). Their decisions tend to favor immediate rewards or functional benefits over long-term satisfaction, leading to frequent brand switching driven by trend adaptation, peer influence and evolving preferences (Shezi & Redda, 2022; Nursilowati & Mayangsari, 2020).

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

This research aimed to examine the influence of SIC, CE, and IM on CS and BL among Indonesian Generation Z in the local footwear market. Unlike findings in developed countries, these factors showed no significant effect on brand loyalty in this context. Instead, price sensitivity, trend adaptation, and functional benefits emerged as dominant factors of Gen Z's purchasing behavior, indicating a shift away from emotional or identity-based loyalty. These findings underscore the importance of pragmatic motivations and the need for marketing strategies focused on affordability, accessibility, and trend responsiveness. Given the limited relevance of traditional constructs like SIC

and CE in this market, localized approaches are essential. The study offers a specific understanding of Indonesian consumer behavior and provides a foundation for future research with larger, more diverse samples to explore brand loyalty in emerging markets and identify additional factors influencing purchase decisions.

Future studies could broaden the scope by including various socio-economic segments to explore how financial background shapes brand loyalty. Longitudinal research could also capture evolving behaviors over time, especially in response to new marketing trends. Additionally, examining moderating or mediating variables such as peer influence, perceived value, or brand trust, and the interplay between global and local brands, could provide deeper insights into loyalty dynamics in emerging markets.

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